

Characterization of Global Error Rate's Role in the Quality of CATIA V5 Structural Simulation Results

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Abstract

The growing competition to compress Development Time of an Electromechanical Product mainly in Automotive Industry has resulted into more focus on pre-validation of Product Design which is also called Design Verification. It involves mainly verifying the Product with end customer boundary conditions into Simulation Tool and predict the behaviour after application of defined load cases without building and testing on actual physical samples. Simply called Computer Aided Engineering (CAE) this not only gives confidence to the Product Designer but also saves lot of time and cost involved in the iterative physical testing. Now as this verification is crucial, so it is also important to understand if results are reliable enough to implement the findings into our Product Design. This paper focus mainly on quality of Simulation Results in CATIA V5 by characterization of Global Error Rate and it's impact on different simulation set-up and parameters.

Keywords: Catia, Structural Stimulation, Quality, Electromechanical

1. Introduction

Generative Structural Analysis in CATIA V5 is a CAD integrated analysis feature which allows designers to understand how their designs behave and to accurately calculate the displacements and stresses within the part or assembly under a variety of loading conditions. This feature is ideal for designers who are not experts in finite element analysis (FEA). With general expertise this feature helps to understand behaviour of the Product under general load cases. The tight integration of the CATIA Structural Analysis solution within the CAD environment allows design-analysis iterations to be performed rapidly by designers working within the CATIA design environment. It enables linear stress and modal analysis on parts and hybrid assemblies, including surfaces, solids, and wireframe geometries.

Generative Structural Analysis allows you to rapidly perform first order mechanical analysis for 3D systems. This workbench is composed of the following products:

- Generative Part Structural Analysis (GPS) allows designers to understand how their designs behave and to accurately calculate the displacements and stresses within the part under a variety of loading conditions. It also allows the vibration characteristics of parts to be assessed by calculating the natural

frequencies and the associated mode shapes. Analyses can be performed on volume parts, surface parts and wireframe geometries.

- Generative Assembly Structural Analysis (GAS) extends the capability of GPS, allowing designers to analyse assemblies as well as individual parts. The analysis of assemblies, including an accurate representation of the way the parts interact and are connected, allows for more realistic and accurate simulation. The designer does not have to make simplifying assumptions about the loading and restraints acting on an individual part. Instead, the part can be analyzed within the environment that it operates with the loading automatically determined based on the way the part is connected to and interacts with surrounding parts.

The biggest advantage of using CATIA for design validation is the associativity with CATIA parts. Any change in CATIA parts (Geometry, Material Assigned) are immediately reflected in the finite element analysis scenario. As the required steps are very simple, the designer will be able to perform simple finite element analysis of the parts and see the effect of change on the strength of the geometry. By default, CATIA uses the Elfini solver for finite element analysis. Elfini Structural Analysis (EST)

Figure 1: Product License in CATIA V5

2. Simulation Process in CATIA V5

The overall process can be subdivided into smaller steps as shown in the illustration.

1. Pre-Processing
2. Computation
3. Post-Processing
4. Meshing & Mesh Refinement Iterations
5. Create Reports

2.1. Pre-Processing

In this step, the actual physical problem is converted into equivalent Finite Element problem. Simply saying, Pre-processing is the stage of the engineering simulation process where engineers create the simulation model. For the simulation setup to be accurate, you need to know what the physics involved in the problem statement is and what is to be solved.

- The complex physical structure is converted into an equivalent Finite Element (FE) model.
- The actual material properties are defined for FE model.
- Actual physical Forces are converted into equivalent FE Loads.
- The actual physical Boundary Conditions are converted into equivalent FE Boundary Conditions.

Figure 2: Pre-Processing

2.2. Computation

The FE problem provided by the pre-processing step is solved to find out the unknown displacement values. Standard FE solution procedures use the data provided by the pre-processing step.

The FE model is solved to find out the unknown displacement values.

Common examples of computations are mathematical equations and computer algorithms.

2.3. Post-Processing

Post-processors import the result files from the solvers and provide the environments and the tools to create comprehensive reports through model visualization and charts.

In CATIA V5 Analysis, using these displacement values from computation, strains and stresses are calculated for the complete structure. You can study the deformation of structure, variation of strains and stresses throughout the structure.

2.4. Meshing and Mesh Refinement Iterations

A mesh is one of the fundamental elements of a simulation process in finite element analysis (FEA). It is a network formed of cells and points (or nodes). Meshing is the method of generating a 2D or 3D grid over a geometry to discretize it and analyse it with simulation.

There are two types of solid elements available in CATIA V5: **linear** and **parabolic**.

Both are referred to as tetrahedron elements and shown below.

Figure 3: Tetra Elements

The linear tetrahedron elements are faster computationally but less accurate. Linear elements have only corner nodes, straight edges, and planar faces.

On the other hand, the parabolic elements require more computational resources but lead to more accurate results. Another important feature of parabolic elements is that they can fit curved surfaces better. An additional mid-edge nodes to each element aid in the approximation of model curvature by enabling the mesh elements to flex at the added nodes. This ability to flex enables the elements to conform to curved model surfaces better. They have higher order shape function.

Figure 4: Tetra Element Basics

The concept of element size is self-explanatory. A smaller element size leads to more accurate results at the expense of a larger computation time. The “sag” terminology is unique to CATIA. In FEA, the geometry of a part is approximated with the elements. The surface of the part and the FEA approximation of a part do not coincide. The “sag” parameter controls the deviation between the two. Therefore, a smaller “sag” value could lead to better results. There is a relationship between these parameters that one does not have to be concerned with at this point.

In its simplest form, mesh refinement is the process of resolving the model with successively finer and finer meshes, comparing the results between these different meshes.

The first solution provides initial estimation of stress / strain values. To get a more accurate solution, the mesh needs to be refined and the computation is to be done again. Because when the mesh is refined, the computation is always invalidated.

Several mesh refinement and computation iterations are performed till the required solution accuracy is achieved.

Linear Element Type

Parabolic Element Type

Highlighted Red Nodes for element function

- Additional mid node for each element edge.
- More computational time.
- Accurate Results.

Figure 5: Element visualization in CATIA V5

2.5. Create Reports

Once the required accuracy level is achieved, various plots such as Displacement, Principle Stress, Von-Mises Stress can be obtained.

3. Global Error Rate in CATIA V5

The ‘Global Error Rate’ sensor in CATIA V5 Structural Simulation Load cases indicates overall accuracy of the solution. It is a good indicator of the reliability of simulation results. In each Mesh Refinement step, the ‘Global Error Rate’ decreases which also makes it a parameter which designer should observe carefully in consecutive simulation iterations. Additionally, the ‘Error in energy’ value should be in order of $10e-8$.

Figure 6: Global Error Rate in Specification Tree

Always consider the Global Error Rate (%) to verify the reliability of your solution/results. This is important part of Post Processing never to be neglected.

As a thumb Rule always remember that Global Error Rate (%) should be less than 10%. The higher the value the more we lose on the reliability of the simulation results.

To get this value in good range please try to focus on below attributes: -

1. Element type
2. Element Size
3. Mesh refinement considered over the load application areas. Areas which have important stress gradient must be refined with a finer mesh.

The Catia FEA module is linear calculation only. Specially if the Yield strength will reach the max. material value, you need to be very carefully. In combination with the high error rate, it's not possible to trust the simulation value.

Below you will see example of impact of mesh refinement on Global Error Rate % on a simple cantilever beam load case: -

Mesh Refinement	No Of Nodes	No Of Elements	% Global Error	CPU Time (sec)
Size=1000, sag=4	117	36	5.677	0.002
Size=500, sag=4	580	243	5.350	0.06
Size=200, sag=4	2557	1492	4.952	0.8
size=100, sag=4	15935	9382	3.206	2e+1
size=50, sag=4	64714	40449	2.363	5e+2
size=30, sag=4	198075	123953	1.812	6e+3

Figure 7: Global Error Rate improvement

As you can see, while refining the global mesh size, Global Error Rate is reducing, and solver time is increasing. Also, it depends on the analyst to judge the result based on these iterations. For example, if the Stress and Displacement values remain unchanged even while refining the mesh size and thus the global error, then we can judge also to rely on initial results with optimum mesh size with CPU time 0.8 seconds.

4. Global Error Rate Characterization with Problem Statement

Let us consider a problem Statement of Cantilever Beam Load case.

Problem Specification

Consider the beam in the figure below. It is clamped on the left side and has a point force of 8kN acting downward on the right end of the beam. The beam has a length of 4 meters, width of 0.346 meters and height of 0.346 meters (cross-section is a square). Additionally, the beam is composed of a material which has a Young's Modulus of 2.8×10^{10} Pa. Using ANSYS, calculate the following:

1. Deformation of the beam
2. Maximum bending stress along the beam
3. Bending moment along the beam

Material Property: -

Young's Modulus	2.8E+10	Pa
Poisson's Ratio	0.4	

4.1. Pre-Analysis (Theoretical Calculation)

We'll start by carrying out hand calculations to predict the expected maximum bending stress and deformation.

We'll later compare the CATIA values to these hand-calculation results.

Calculate the Maximum Bending Stress at $x=0m$

The maximum bending stress is calculated using Euler-Bernoulli beam theory.

$$\sigma_{max} = \frac{M(x)Y}{I}$$

$$I = \frac{bh^3}{12}$$

$$\sigma_{max} = \frac{(8000N)(4m) \left(\frac{.346m}{2} \right)}{\frac{(0.346m)(0.346m)^3}{12}} = 4.635MPa$$

Calculate the Total Deformation at x=4m

$$u'' = \frac{M}{EI}, \quad u'(0) = 0, \quad u(0) = 0$$

$$M = PL \left(1 - \frac{x}{L} \right)$$

$$u'' = \frac{PL}{EI} \left(1 - \frac{x}{L} \right)$$

$$u' = \int u'' dx = \int \frac{PL}{EI} \left(1 - \frac{x}{L} \right) dx = \frac{PL}{EI} \left(x - \frac{x^2}{2L} \right) + C_1$$

$$u'(0) = 0 \quad \therefore \quad u' = \frac{PL}{EI} \left(x - \frac{x^2}{2L} \right)$$

$$u = \int u' dx = \int \frac{PL}{EI} \left(x - \frac{x^2}{2L} \right) dx = \frac{PL}{EI} \left(\frac{x^2}{2} - \frac{x^3}{6L} \right) + C_2$$

$$u(0) = 0 \quad \therefore \quad u = \frac{PL}{EI} \left(\frac{x^2}{2} - \frac{x^3}{6L} \right)$$

$$u(4m) = \frac{(8000N)(4m)}{(2.8 \times 10^{10}) \left(\frac{(0.346m)(0.346m)^3}{12} \right)} \left(\frac{(4m)^2}{2} - \frac{(4m)^3}{6(4m)} \right) = 0.005103m$$

From theoretical calculation, we have: -
Maximum Bending Stress= 4.635 MPa
Total Deformation= 0.005103

Now we will use CATIA V5 Structural Simulation to verify the result and it's quality by considering impact on Global Error Rate %.

4.2. Structural Simulation in CATIA V5

For the problem statement, we will follow below steps for the structural analysis: -

1. Generate Model and Assign Material

2. Applying Boundary Conditions & Solving with mesh size 400 mm
3. Solving using Linear Element with mesh size (400 mm)
 - a. check behaviour of Absolute Sag on Global Error Rate %
4. Solving using Reduced Linear Element size & Local using Local Mesh Size--
 - a. check impact on Global Error Rate %
5. Solving using Parabolic Element Type with mesh size 400 mm
6. Summarize Observation

1. Generate Model and Assign Material

Figure 8: Generate Model

2. Applying Boundary Conditions & Solving with mesh size (400 mm)

Figure 9: Boundary Conditions & solve.

Figure 10: Solve

3. Solving using Linear Element with mesh size (400 mm): Check behaviour of Absolute Sag on Global Error Rate %

Figure 11: Solving with Linear Mesh Size

Observation: -

- No impact of Absolute Sag on Nodes and Elements Formulation
- **No impact of Absolute Sag on Global Error Rate %**
- No impact of Absolute Sag on Results
- Using Linear Element,
 - Maximum Stress = 1.79 MPa
 - Maximum displacement = 1.84 mm
 - Global Error Rate = 60.34%

Results shows larger deviation from theoretical results.

Additionally,

Global Error Rate % is on higher side (60.34%) which means that the Simulation results are not reliable, or the quality of the result is not good.

As per thumb rule, the Global Error Rate % must be less than 10%.

Now in next step, we will try to reduce the mesh size and analyze the impact on Global Error Rate % and the results.

Consecutively, we can deactivate the absolute sag as it has no impact on output parameters.

4. Solving using Reduced Linear Element size & using Local Mesh Size: Check impact on Global Error Rate %

Reduced Element Size

Figure 9: Solving with Reduced Linear Mesh Size

Local Mesh Size

Global Element Size: 100 mm
No Local Definition

Global Error Rate (%)
Global Error Rate (%) = 36.060741425

Global Element Size: 100 mm
Local Element Size: 5 mm (on 2 faces)

Global Error Rate (%)
Global Error Rate (%) = 35.831134796

Figure 12: Solving with Local Linear Mesh Size

Observation: -

Global Error Rate reduces after reducing element size and introducing local mesh size.

Using Linear Element with Reduced Element Sizes,

Maximum Stress = 9.11 MPa

Maximum displacement = 4.9 mm

Global Error Rate Reduced = 18%

Solver Time increased up to 7 mins for element size less than 10 mm.

Stress Results shows larger deviation from theoretical results in case mesh size is reduced to 10mm or less.

Displacement value approaches to theoretical result with reduced mesh size.

Reason: Percentage of error is by far less for deflection as compared to von-mises stress. According to Finite Element Analysis theory, stresses are not predicted as accurately as displacement. Stress is derived and averaged. Large variation in von-mises stress is due stress concentration at edges of beam.

Global Error Rate remains higher than 10%.

To get better characterization of results recommendation is: -

- 1/ Use parabolic element type
- 2/ Use coarse mesh size instead of fine mesh

5. Solving using Parabolic Element Type with Coarse Mesh Size 400 mm

Figure 13: Solving with Parabolic Element

Observation: -

By using Parabolic Element Type with same element size as considered in Linear, we get better results much closer to theoretical results.

Also, Global error rate decreases below 10% which is quite reliable.

Here also refer one example: -

Meshing with Parabolic Element Type has reliable Global Error Rate for defined load case.
Computation time increases in Parabolic Case by 8 seconds.

Figure 14: Solving with Parabolic Element (Example)

6. Summarize Observation

So, with the case ‘Solving using Parabolic Element Type with Coarse Mesh Size’ has best result close to theoretical values. It means that using Parabolic Element Type has maximum impact on Global Error Rate % and quality of results. The solver time is increased here as a greater number of partial differential equations in background need to solve, but results will be accurate.

Depending on the complexity of model the designer needs to decide the mesh size and usage of local mesh refinement for area of interests.

The Global Error Rate % here can help to understand the result quality and simplify the intent of designer during decision making situations.

5. Conclusion

Verification and validation (V&V) are essential steps for evaluating the accuracy and reliability of your CAE simulations. Verification is the process of checking whether your CAE simulations are implemented correctly and free of numerical errors. Validation is the process of comparing your CAE simulations with experimental data, analytical solutions, or other sources of reference to determine whether they represent the reality of your problem. By conducting V&V, you can ensure that your CAE simulations are credible and trustworthy for your CAM design and manufacturing.

The accuracy and reliability of your CAE simulations depend largely on the models and methods that you use. You need to choose appropriate models and methods that match the physics, geometry, boundary conditions, and loading scenarios of your problem statement. You also need to consider the trade-offs between complexity, accuracy, and computational cost. With this study it is important to understand features in simulation itself to understand the quality of the solution. In CATIA V5 we call it Global Error and in some other CAE software might be referred with different name, but intent is same which is reach the best solution on which we can rely.

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Validation as next step is also an integral part of the FEA process that ensures the accuracy and reliability of simulation results. It provides engineers and researchers with confidence in their models, enables informed decision-making, and contributes to the overall success and safety of engineering projects.